

THE EU SAFE COUNTRIES OF ORIGIN LIST: A FAST TRACK TO IRREGULARITY

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Key issues

- The European Parliament and the EU Council have recently found a political agreement on a EU-wide 'Safe' Countries of Origin List.
- The 'safety' of countries is not the main criterium behind their designations. Instead, it is based on political and practical convenience.
- The adoption of the EU-wide list has mainly a political value.
- This policy is likely to result in an increased number of irregularised migrants.
- Only a genuinely bona fide implementation of the safeguards related to the safe country of origin concept can diminish (but not erase) the risk of undermining the access to international protection.

The European Parliament and the European Council have recently found a [political agreement](#) to adopt a EU-wide list of 'safe' countries of origin. A 'safe' country of origin is a country where it is generally *assumed* that there is no risk of persecution or indiscriminate violence. The consequence is that asylum seekers coming from these countries have lowered guarantees in the asylum procedure. For example, their claim can be assessed in the context of an accelerated procedure.

The 'safe' country of origin concept has been part of EU asylum legislation since 2005, and most of EU member states already have their own national list of safe countries of origin. Since the establishment of the Common European Asylum System, the EU has sought to harmonise the application of this concept by adopting a common (minimum) safe countries of origin list. If adopted, this would be the first list of this kind.

In this policy brief, we examine the proposed EU safe countries of origin list and question both its rationale and likelihood to achieve the stated objective. We show that the countries that are in the EU list have not been included on the ground of genuine human rights considerations, but for reasons of practical and political convenience. We argue that the adoption of a common EU list is unlikely to harmonise significantly safe country of origin lists and practices across member states. Rather, its main effect will be political: to legitimise and encourage a broader use of the safe country of origin policy. We also hold that an increased application of the safe country of origin policy risks producing human rights violations, irregularisation and administration overburdening. We conclude that while the bona fide implementation of safeguards related to the implementation of safe countries of origin policies may mitigate these negative effects, it cannot fully prevent the risk of undermining the access to international protection.

HOW 'SAFE' ARE THE COUNTRIES IN THE PROPOSED EU LIST?

The proposed EU safe countries of origin list includes **Bangladesh, Colombia, Egypt, India, Kosovo, Morocco and Tunisia** as well as all the current EU candidate countries: **Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Georgia, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Türkiye**. Quite clearly, not all of these countries respond to 'safety' criteria. Instead, **several of these countries have serious and ongoing human rights issues**, ranging from political repression and arbitrary detention to enforced disappearances, structural discrimination, ongoing armed conflict and discrimination and violence against LGBTQIA+ individuals and other marginalised groups.

If not based on human rights considerations – as also argued [elsewhere](#) – **the reasons behind the insertion of these countries in the list appear to be rather of a practical and political nature**. For example, EU candidate countries seem to be in the list as a necessary step in view of their future integration into the Common European Asylum System. Similarly, countries such as Egypt, Morocco and Tunisia have probably been selected as they have recently been the target of a consistent EU effort to boost cooperation on migration – including on returns. Finally, countries such as Bangladesh and Colombia are evidently in the list because applications from these countries are on a significant rise.

This rationale behind the proposed EU list is not surprising. Both previous studies and our own project on safe country of origin policies in EU member states show that, historically, these types of reasons have always been behind most of the existing national safe countries of origin lists.

WHAT WILL CHANGE WITH THE ADOPTION OF THE EU LIST?

We argue that the EU-wide safe countries of origin list, if adopted, will not have a substantial impact on EU member states 'safe' countries of origin national lists. The proposed list is short and, most importantly, is a minimum standard: once adopted, Member States will remain free to add additional countries to their own national lists. Most EU member states, in fact, already have national lists of safe countries of origin – many of which are considerably more extensive than the one proposed by the EU. Moreover, the majority of countries included in the proposed EU list are already classified as 'safe', or there is already the intention to do so, by the main destination countries of these applicants. Finally, in the context of the upcoming entry into force, in summer 2026, of the new Pact on Migration and Asylum, the application of an accelerated procedure and other lowered guarantees in the asylum procedure will no

longer depend primarily on a country's designation as a 'safe' country of origin. They will depend instead on the recognition rate (under 20%).

The adoption of a EU list is therefore unlikely to result in any meaningful constraint on, or harmonisation of, national practices. Rather, **we expect that its value will be mainly political**. First, the EU list will reinforce the legitimacy of the already existing – and often contested – national designations. This move may encourage member states to dismiss more easily the claims coming from applicants from 'safe' countries of origin.

Secondly, classifying these countries of origin as 'safe' is a political signal that they are a priority for return operations, alongside the current efforts to streamline return cooperation among member states and with migrants' countries of origin. Overall, the adoption of the EU safe countries of origin list is part of a package of other restrictive measures, which includes a more stringent [return regulation](#) and a reinforced use of the safe third (or [fourth](#)) country policy.

The [stated objective](#) of adopting the EU list – and in general of implementing safe country of origin policies – is to streamline asylum procedures and return rejected applicants faster. However, we argue that this decision is likely to produce the opposite outcome. Return rates from EU countries are generally [low](#), irrespective of existing readmission agreements with third countries. For this reason, we expect that a reinforced application of the safe country of origin concept will further **exacerbate existing dynamics of irregularisation**. While return rates are unlikely to increase, an increasing number of applicants from 'safe' countries will have their claims assessed under reduced procedural safeguards and face a higher risk of rejection. At the same time, we expect that 'safe' countries designation may discourage some applicants from applying for asylum, due to fears of detention and removals, contributing to an increase in undocumented migrants. This dynamic may also result in **overburdening national administrations**, that will be obliged to process the subsequent claims of irregularised asylum seekers over and over again.

AGAINST A 'MECHANISATION' OF ASYLUM DECISIONS

In light of the arguments expressed above, we hold that the adoption of a EU-wide safe countries of origin lists is not justified on human rights grounds. Moreover, the new regulation on asylum procedures – that will enter into force in summer 2026 – and its [potential amendments](#) already significantly lower the human rights criteria and guarantees for applying the safe country of origin concept. For all these reasons, it appears that there is no possibility of applying safe countries of origin policies without a significant risk of undermining the right to asylum, producing irregularisation and overburdening national administrations.

The *bona fide* implementation of the safeguards related to the implementation of safe countries of origin policies may, however, mitigate these negative effects. For example, an effective delisting mechanism at both EU and national levels must be fully operational in practice, ensuring the prompt removal of countries from the list in the event of armed conflict or serious deterioration of the human rights situation. Equally crucial is the preservation of a truly individualised assessment. Even in the context of an accelerated procedure, applicants originating from designated 'safe' countries must continue to have their claims examined on a case-by-case basis, in line with international law and the Refugee Convention. Particular attention should also be devoted to timely identifying persons in situations of vulnerability, whose protection requires enhanced procedural safeguards. Applying these safeguards may diminish – but not erase – the risk of a 'mechanisation' of asylum decisions, where applicants coming from 'safe' countries have very little chances of obtaining protection, regardless of their protection needs.

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